

The Influence of Democratic Leadership on Performance of Employees in The Population and Civil Records Office of Binjai City

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of democratic leadership on employee performance at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was 61 employees from the total number of employees. The research results show that democratic leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is shown by the T-value of $8.389 > t$ table 1.67109 with a P-Value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The regression coefficient shows that if democratic leadership is increased by 1 unit, employee performance will increase by 1,549 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.536 or 53.60%, which indicates that democratic leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, democratic leadership has a positive and significant effect on the work of employees at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office. This identifies that improvements in democratic leadership can contribute to improved employee performance.

Keywords: Democratic Leadership; Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Organizations in achieving their goals rely heavily on the contribution of human resources, namely their members or employees. Whether in planning, organizing, directing, coordinating or supervising, employee behavior, both individually and in groups, can have a significant impact on organizational performance. Although there are many factors that contribute to achieving organizational performance, employee work behavior is the most important and determining factor (Mas'ud, 2004). Therefore, individual employee performance will make a significant contribution to the overall performance of the organization.

Performance is the result of an employee's work in an organization or company (Alviani & Saraswati, 2021). According to (Wibowo, 2013), performance comes from the definition of performance. There are also those who define performance as the result of work or work achievement. However, performance actually has a broader meaning, not just the results of work, but including how the work process takes place.

Even though employee work behavior has a significant impact on organizational performance, in reality in every organization there is still a lack of understanding of the relationship between democratic leadership, employee performance and organizational commitment for each employee (Yunianto et al., 2020). Many previous studies have highlighted the importance of democratic leadership in improving employee performance but have not fully paid attention to the role of organizational commitment as a mediator in this relationship. Therefore, there is a knowledge gap regarding how exactly democratic

leadership influences employee performance through organizational commitment as an intervention mechanism.

Based on initial observations made by the author through observations and interviews with the Head of the Binjai City Population and Civil Records Office, the phenomenon that occurs is that democratic leadership has not been implemented optimally for all employees. Another thing that happens is that although each employee has their own responsibilities, it cannot be ascertained whether their performance is optimal.

According to (Afandi, 2018) employee performance is the work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics.

Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara. AA P, 2020) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or that apply within the organization.

To measure employee performance, this research refers to theory (Afandi, 2018) which is as follows:

- 1) Quantity of work output;
- 2) Quality of work results;
- 3) Efficiency in carrying out tasks;
- 4) Work discipline;
- 5) Initiative ;
- 6) Accuracy;
- 7) Leadership;
- 8) Honesty; And
- 9) Creativity.

To achieve maximum performance, many factors can influence it. This research is limited to democratic leadership factors. Democratic leadership is active, dynamic and directed leadership. Control activities are carried out in an orderly and responsible manner. The division of tasks accompanied by a clear delegation of authority and responsibility allows each member to participate actively (Olla, 2017).

In this research, the definition of democratic leadership refers to Woods' opinion in (Turmono, 2020) which states that democratic leadership is the ability to influence other people to cooperate in achieving predetermined goals by means of various activities that will be carried out jointly determined by the leader and subordinates.

In this research, the indicators of democratic leadership refer to Susanti's opinion in (Turmono, 2020), namely:

- 1) The ability to encourage subordinates to use their cognitive and reasoning powers in solving various problems faced.
- 2) Encourage the use of innovation and creativity in carrying out tasks.

- 3) Leaders and subordinates are both involved in decision making or problem solving.
- 4) The relationship between leaders and subordinates is well established.

The aim of this research is to analyze and identify the influence of democratic leadership on employee performance at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registration Service,

It is hoped that the results of this research will provide a deeper understanding of the dynamics of the relationship between democratic leadership and employee performance at the Population and Civil Registry Service of Binjai City, Binjai City. It is hoped that the implications of this research will provide valuable insight for organizational leaders and management in improving employee performance through developing democratic leadership. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office, totaling 61 people with the following details.

Table 1. Population Details at the Population and Civil Service Office Binjai City Civil Registry

No.	Employee Status	Number of people)
1.	ASN	23
2.	Honorary	38
Amount		61

Source: Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to Sugiyono (2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 61 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Democratic Leadership

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely democratic leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Democratic Leadership	61	3.50	5.00	4.4262	.46936

Employee Performance	61	3.30	5.00	4.3164	.45760
Valid N (listwise)	61				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess democratic leadership and employee performance at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office as above average, with mean values of 4,426 and 4,316 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.469 for democratic leadership and 0.457 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perceptions, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for the Democratic Leadership Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.847 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.916 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.893 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.890 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the democratic leadership variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.251 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the democratic leadership variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.909 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.918 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.794 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.821 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.5	0.780 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.6	0.826 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.7	0.786 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.8	0.838 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.9	0.882 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2521 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Democratic leadership	0.907	4
Employee Performance	0.944	9

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the democratic leadership and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10,712	3,374		3,175	,002
Democratic Leadership	1,594	,190	,738	8,389	,000

Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 10,712 + 1.594X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 10.712 means that if there is no democratic leadership, then there is an employee performance of 10.712 points. The regression coefficient for democratic leadership is 1.594, meaning that democratic leadership influences an increase in employee performance by 1.594 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.738a	.544	.536	2.79088	.544	70,371	1	59	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Democratic Leadership

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.536 or 53.60%, which means that democratic leadership has a moderate influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.536 or 53.60%, which means that democratic leadership has a moderate influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of democratic leadership on employee performance at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office

Ha: There is an influence of democratic leadership on employee performance at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10,712	3,374		3,175	.002
Democratic leadership	1,594	.190	.738	8,389	.000

Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $8.389 > t$ table 1.67109 , with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between democratic leadership on employee performance at the Population Service Office. and Binjai City Civil Registry.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Democratic Leadership on Employee Performance, these findings are in line with research results (Sitio & Arwiyah, 2023), (Ferils & Utami, 2022) which show that Democratic leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

These findings underline the importance of democratic leadership in improving employee performance. Leadership that involves employee participation and involvement in decision making can have a positive and significant impact on overall organizational performance (Djaluputro & Andrias, 2023).

The implication of these findings is that organizations can consider implementing a democratic leadership approach in their managerial structure. This can be done by providing opportunities for employees to participate in the decision-making process, increasing their sense of ownership and involvement in achieving organizational goals.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the hypothesis test show that democratic leadership has a positive effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the T-count value of $8.389 > t$ table 1.67109, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if democratic leadership is increased by 1 unit, then changes in employee performance as seen from the Y value will increase by 1.594 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially democratic leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office.
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.536 or 53.60%, which means that democratic leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the discussion and conclusions above, the following suggestions can be implemented by the Binjai City Population and Civil Registry Office to improve employee performance and organizational commitment:

1. Institutions are expected to be able to implement democratic leadership principles consistently at all levels of management. By involving employees in the decision-making process.
2. Institutions must also carry out a comprehensive evaluation of various factors that influence employee performance, such as competence, intrinsic motivation, support from superiors, and working conditions. Evaluation results, policies and strategies can

be adjusted to strengthen these factors, create a conducive and motivating work environment, and help employees achieve optimal performance.

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